

Original article

Hematological Profile in Donkey Depending on Lactation

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Abstract

The factors that influence the hematological profile of the donkeys are: nutrition, reproduction, season, lactation, parturition, maintenance and animal health. Knowing the hematological parameters represents a breakthrough in the development of work programs and nutritional programs in the donkey farms and greatly helps the possibility of the conservation of the donkeys, a species that until now has been neglected in our country. For haematological parameters, significant changes can be observed under the influence of lactation as follows: WBC (G/L) may have a lower mean average in lactation I, (9.66 ± 0.56) and further in lactation, reaching a higher value average in lactation IV (13.57 ± 0.80). Hb (g/L) behaves similar to WBC, reaching the highest average values in IV lactation, (131.30 ± 3.56). LYM (%) in lactation I, (38.72 ± 0.69) and in lactation 2, 3 and 4 similar average values. MON (%) manifests thus, under the influence of lactation, having an interval between (1.14 ± 0.16), lactation I and (1.42 ± 0.17) in lactation IV.

Keywords: donkey, haematological parameters, lactation.

1. Introduction

Hematological parameters depend on several factors: physiological status, management, hygiene in the unit, animal feed, lactation, breed, species. Hematological analyzes of blood are aimed primarily at monitoring the health status and for detecting diseases [5, 19, 20]. The assessment and monitoring of the physiological parameters is essential to be able to evaluate the health of the animals in terms of lactation. The content of blood components varies depending on the factors that inhibit or stimulate circulation.

The main function of the blood is to maintain the physiological balance of the body, while the blood hematological indicators are the main determining factor for the health and welfare of the animals [1, 21, 22].

The determination of hematological parameters is a basic test, being one of the most frequent laboratory tests, often representing the first step in establishing the hematological status and the diagnosis of various haematological conditions and other types of conditions [2, 17, 18, 30].

The purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of lactation on haematological parameters in the donkey.

2. Material and Method

Blood samples were collected from each donkey for haematological analysis and were analyzed within 12 hours of collection.

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A number of 15 samples were collected for each lactation (lactation I, II, III and IV). The freshly harvested blood was analyzed for the determination of hematological parameters, with automatic Abacus Junior Vet, Diatron, Messtechnik. It takes 25 μ l of test sample. The animals from this study come from the areal of Sălaj and Cluj.

3. Results and Discussions

Tables 1 and 2 show average values and variability for haematological parameters in donkey for lactation I-IV. WBC (G/L) in lactation 1 shows the

mean value 9.66 ± 0.56 g/L and 13.57 ± 0.80 g/L in lactation 4 (Tables 1 and 2). These values are in agreement with those published by [20] regarding the haematological parameters in the donkey.

Hb shows an average value of 114.08 ± 2.89 (g/L) in lactation 1 and Hb increases reaching the highest values in lactation 4, 131.30 ± 3.56 (g/L) (Tables 1 and 2).

These values are within the limits allowed for this parameter.

The hematological values obtained in this study for lactating donkeys are in agreement with those reported in other studies [6, 7, 21].

Table 1. Mean value and variability for haematological parameters in donkey depending on lactation (lactation I - II)

Parameter	Lactation I (n=15)		Lactation II (n=15)	
	X \pm sx	V%	X \pm sx	V%
WBC (G/L)	9.66 \pm 0.56	13.04	11.27 \pm 0.59	11.65
RBC (T/L)	5.96 \pm 0.5	18.72	6.03 \pm 0.35	12.89
Hb (g/L)	114.08 \pm 2.89	5.67	121.54 \pm 4.89	9.0
HCT L/L)	0.37 \pm 0.07	43.92	0.21 \pm 0.02	22.14
MCV (fL)	52.56 \pm 2.94	12.49	61.78 \pm 3.07	11.11
NEU (%)	34.54 \pm 1.60	10.33	39.82 \pm 1.91	10.72
LYM (%)	38.72 \pm 0.69	3.98	52.44 \pm 4.15	17.71
MON (%)	1.14 \pm 0.16	30.68	1.41 \pm 0.07	11.83
MON (g/L)	0.03 \pm 0.01	6.75	0.09 \pm 0.01	32.39
NEU (g/L)	2.92 \pm 0.16	12.30	3.03 \pm 0.16	12.04
LYM (g/L)	4.16 \pm 0.28	14.92	5.18 \pm 0.34	14.54
EOS (%)	2.81 \pm 0.09	6.90	3.94 \pm 0.42	23.68
PLT (g/L)	2.18 \pm 0.10	10.24	2.27 \pm 0.26	25.64
MCHC (g/L)	317.68 \pm 4.53	3.19	313.58 \pm 6.03	3.73
BAS (%)	0.01 \pm 0.01	27.66	0.05 \pm 0.01	13.85

V- variability; X - average value; n- number of blood samples.

Table 2. Mean value and variability for haematological parameters in donkey depending on lactation (lactation III-IV)

Parameter	Lactation III (n=15)		Lactation IV (n=15)	
	X \pm sx	V%	X \pm sx	V%
WBC (G/L)	12.28 \pm 0.85	15.54	13.57 \pm 0.80	13.26
RBC (T/L)	7.49 \pm 0.46	13.71	6.61 \pm 0.32	10.97
Hb (g/l)	124.98 \pm 3.27	5.85	131.30 \pm 3.56	6.06
HCT (L/L)	0.30 \pm 0.04	27.94	0.37 \pm 0.03	20.86
MCV (fL)q	64.23 \pm 1.98	6.89	67.46 \pm 0.87	2.89
NEU (%)	48.58 \pm 1.13	5.19	51.08 \pm 2.23	9.76
LYM (%)	52.98 \pm 2.96	12.48	52.36 \pm 3.08	13.17
MON (%)	1.38 \pm 0.09	15.38	1.42 \pm 0.17	26.87
MON (g/L)	0.13 \pm 0.02	28.76	0.16 \pm 0.02	27.13
NEU (g/L)	3.38 \pm 0.19	12.45	3.65 \pm 0.17	10.57
LYM (g/L)	7.19 \pm 0.34	10.47	7.17 \pm 0.36	11.13
EOS (%)	5.02 \pm 0.47	20.99	4.90 \pm 0.08	3.82
PLT (g/L)	2.67 \pm 0.21	17.16	2.37 \pm 0.14	12.83
MCHC (g/L)	361.58 \pm 6.03	3.73	380.96 \pm 5.42	3.18
BAS (%)	0.11 \pm 0.01	25.69	0.15 \pm 0.01	21.98

V- variability; X - average value; n- number of blood samples.

Knowing hematological values is useful in diagnosing metabolic and pathological disorders that may occur in farm animals [13, 16, 19, 23, 24, 28]. Advanced lactation influences the level of hemoglobin in the blood. In the case of animals in advanced gestation, decreases for hemoglobin are observed [9]. Variations in the level of leukocytes have been observed in various studies such as those reported by [9, 11, 12, 25].

In the study conducted by Hoff and Duffield in 2003 [19], no significant changes in the haematological parameters are shown, only in the case of hemoglobin and erythrocytes (especially in pregnant animals). These aspects were in agreement with other studies [26, 27, 28].

Befus and Denburg (2004), and Horáčková et al. (2017) report higher values for MCH in adult animals compared to those in the young group. It observed higher values for haematological parameters for late lactation and lower for early lactation [4, 20].

The average values for WBC (g/L), RBC (T/L), NEU (%), LYM (%), Hb (g/L) and MCV (fL) are in agreement with those published in the literature [5, 6, 13, 19, 20, 25] Monitoring these parameters can lead to the provision of extremely useful information and the development of a handbook, a useful clinical guide on monitoring the health of lactating donkeys [8]. The most important hematological parameters increased in relation to other experimental groups and in comparison with the parameters determined in the blood at the beginning of the process, ie before the beginning of grazing [10, 26].

Feeding on pasture has a positive effect on the basic hematological parameters and, consequently, on the welfare of the animals destined for milk production [10, 26]. The mean values for MCV and Hb are in agreement with those published by [10]. Horáčková et al. (2017) present for MCV and MCH in donkeys under three years, lower values [20]. LYM showed lower values in donkeys under ten years, similar to those reported by [10].

Horáčková et al. (2017) report changes in the biochemical parameters of blood under the influence of age [20]. Average values for MCHC (g/L) depending on lactation and falls in the range of 317.68 ± 4.53 (g/L) in lactation 1 and 380.96 ± 5.42 (g/L) in lactation 4. PLT (G/L) has similar values in lactation 1, 2 and 4 and higher in lactation 3. These values are in agreement with those published in the following studies [20, 24, 25]. Erythrocyte number is influenced by changes in plasma volume, such as in pregnancy [8, 10, 23].

The developmental origins of health and disease are a fundamental paradigm for the investigation and understanding of many metabolic diseases [3, 7, 17, 18, 20]. In short, environmental

signals have the potential to alter the developmental pathways of an organism as a physiological result and on metabolism, which is strongly affected by these signals. Thus, the physiological health status is largely modeled by the factors that intervene during the intrauterine life. Horáčková et al. (2017) report higher values for NEU in donkeys over 10 years old [20]. These assertions are contrary to those reported by other studies such as [7, 10], which states that this parameter decreases as the body ages.

MCV, MCH, TP, CREA, show significant changes according to gender. MCH and MCV showed higher values in females [20]. In the study reported by Barker in 1998 [3]. He observed higher values for MCH and MCHC in male donkeys. It observes lower values for Hb in donkeys and higher values for RBC in donkeys and lower for RBC in males [1, 15, 22].

Leukocytes increased in advanced gestation in milk animals, compared to animals in early lactation where lower values were observed for this parameter. Hematological, biochemical parameters, nutritional and metabolic parameters give us information about the health of farm animals [10]. Lactation and gestation period influence blood biochemistry, these aspects are altered due to the endocrine and metabolic influence that accompany these periods (gestation, lactation) [10].

Leukocytosis is usually due to an increase in the number of neutrophils or lymphocytes; less often the other classes of leukocytes increase the absolute number of leukocytes. A proportional increase of all types of leukocytes is due to hemoconcentration [4, 10]. Metabolic profile and blood parameters show significant variations when it comes to animals of different sex and using different management systems, or differently housed. Certain parameters can be used as indicators of changes that occur under the influence of housing and management conditions. These indicators are (MVC, RDW) [27].

The decrease in the number of red blood cells causes anemia. Anemia is functionally defined by an insufficient erythrocyte mass to provide an adequate amount of oxygen to peripheral tissues. RDW-CV and MPV showed higher values in females compared to males [27]. The presence of hematological abnormalities (platelets, leukocyte abnormalities) orient the diagnosis to a possible medullary failure due to anemia, a malignant hematological disease or the dislocation of the bone marrow through pathological processes of extrahematological cause. Increased erythrocyte count (hemoglobin concentration and/or hematocrit) causes erythrocytosis [16, 23, 27, 29].

The hematologic examination of blood can be used as a routine test and for the purpose of diagnosing certain diseases and preventing the

administration with different medicines. Depending on the species, including the donkeys, it can be said that we have specific physiological intervals regarding the blood parameters.

Data on hematological and biochemical profile in donkeys are not sufficient compared to other species [8, 9, 16, 30-31].

4. Conclusions

It can be stated that lactation influences the average values for haematological parameters in the donkey. Most reaching the lowest average values in the first two lactations and the highest in lactations 3 and 4. The hematological parameters studied under the influence of lactation fall within the specific limits published by other authors for this species and taking into account lactation or other influencing factors.

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